

21.9.2023

On the full potential and role of different solar photovoltaic system technologies in the Iberian energy transition

Mai ElSayed¹, Dmitrii Bogdanov¹, Dominik Keiner¹, Lukas Walter², Rasul Satymov¹, Juan Carlos Osorio-Aravena^{3,4}, Christian Breyer¹

¹ LUT University, Finland; ² OTH Regensburg, Germany; ³ Universidad Austral de Chile, Chile;

⁴ University of Jaén, Spain

EU PVSEC 40, Lisbon, September 21, 2023

Energy sector status & targets

Energy & power sectors

- **Total electricity generation** reached **304 TWh** in 2020 in Iberia
- Almost **half** of the electricity was generated from **renewable sources**, of which **wind power** was the most dominant
- **Total primary energy demand** reached **1266 TWh** in 2020 in Iberia
- Contrary to the power sector, only **17%** of **TPED** came from **renewable energy**

Climate targets*

- Latest **EU** nationally determined contribution states a **55% reduction target** (relative to 1990) for **GHG emissions across all sectors by 2030** without accounting for international credits
- A **nation-specific GHG emissions reduction target of 26%** and **17%** applies to **Spain** and **Portugal**, respectively
- **Spain** aims for **net zero emissions by 2050**, via a renewable share of **100%** for **electricity** and **97%** for **total energy mix**
- **Portugal** aims for **net zero emissions by 2050**, via a renewable share of **100%** for **electricity and transport**, and **87%** for **total energy mix**

Share of electricity generation sources - 2020

Share of total primary energy demand sources - 2020

Figure 1. Electricity generation (left) and total primary energy demand (right) by source in Iberia as of 2020.

*sources: <https://unfccc.int/NDCREG>; <https://www.iea.org/reports/spain-2021>; <https://www.iea.org/reports/portugal-2021>

LUT Energy System Transition Model (LUT-ESTM)

source:
[Bogdanov, Breyer et al. 2021, Energy, 227, 120467](#)

recent reports

[link to report](#)

[link to report](#)

[link to report](#)

[link to report](#)

Key features:

- full hourly resolution, applied in global-local studies, comprising about 120 technologies
- used for several major reports, in 60+ scientific studies, published on all levels, including Nature
- strong consideration of all kinds of Power-to-X (heat, fuels, chemicals, materials, freshwater, CO₂, CDR, forests)
- **PV diversity (9 systems):** **prosumers:** RES, COM, IND; **utility:** fixed-tilted, single-axis for both monofacial and bifacial, offshore floating; **agrivoltaics:** vertical

Bifacial PV modelling & validation

Figure 1. Representative sites used for the validation against PVsyst (top), system FLh deviation for each test site and PV technology (bottom left), and linear correlation between LUT-PV and PVsyst results (bottom right).

Validation methodology

- LUT-PV results compared to simulation results from PVsyst v7.3
- 9 representative sites with differing climate conditions used to establish the global validity of the results
- Same meteorological data source used for simulations in LUT-PV and PVsyst
- Validation conducted for fixed-tilted and single-axis tracking systems without backtracking, for both monofacial and bifacial modules

Validation results

- Results of all test sites and PV system technologies lie within a $\pm 4\%$ tolerance band
- LUT-PV usually underperforms PVsyst in case of monofacial/bifacial fixed-tilted PV systems
- LUT-PV usually outperforms PVsyst in case of monofacial/bifacial single-axis tracking PV systems
- Overall, there is a high linear correlation between LUT-PV and PVsyst results

Bifacial PV performance

Figure 2. Aggregated feed-in profiles for monofacial south-facing fixed tilted (left) and single-axis tracking (right) in Spain and Portugal.

Figure 3. Difference in yield, expressed in full load hours (FLh) for an exemplary site in Spain between monofacial and bifacial fixed-tilted solar PV (left) and between bifacial optimally titled south-facing and vertical east-west facing solar PV (right).

- Fixed-tilted south-facing monofacial PV systems reach up to 1800 FLh in the south of Spain and Portugal
- Single-axis tracking south-facing monofacial PV systems reach up to 2200 and 2400 FLh in Portugal and Spain, respectively
- At an exemplary site in Castilla-La Mancha, fixed-tilted south-facing bifacial PV outperforms its monofacial counterpart on daily and annual bases
- The resulting annual yield increase amounts to 90 kWh/kWp, or a 5.3% improvement

>> With a higher performance and similar costs, bifacial PV is expected to dominate new installations in accordance with ITRPV

- At the same site, vertical east-west facing bifacial PV shows a complementary pattern to its fixed-tilted south-facing counterpart
- However, it underperforms fixed-tilted south-facing bifacial PV systems by 347 kWh/kWp on an annual basis

>> This negatively affects the levelised cost of electricity (LCOE) generated by vertical PV and limits it to certain applications, like agrivoltaics with valuable co-benefits

The Iberian energy system transition

- **Model:** LUT-ESTM
 - **Temporal resolution:** Hourly, 5-year interval transition pathway
 - **Spatial resolution:** Sub-national multi-node, based on the first level of the nomenclature of territorial units for statistics (NUTS I)
- >> 10 nodes in total; 7 mainland and 3 island nodes
- **Energy sectors:** Power, heat, transport, industry, desalination, and e-fuels/chemicals export
 - **Sector-coupling:** Full
 - **Electricity trade:** only within Iberia, the whole region is assumed to have energy sovereignty
 - **Target:** zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 (base), and 2040 (ambitious)
 - **Solar PV technologies, 9 in total:**
 1. Prosumers: residential, commercial, and industrial (3)
 2. Utility-scale: mono/bifacial fixed-tilted and single-axis tracking (4)
 3. Agrivoltaics: vertical bifacial (1)
 4. Offshore floating: monofacial (1)
 - **Bifacial PV phase-in:** 25% by 2025, 70% by 2030, and then unrestricted based on the ITRPV projections

* the overall energy-industry system results until 2040 for mainland regions are presented, the full set of results will appear in the peer-reviewed journal version

Figure 4. Spatial scope and resolution of Spain and Portugal used in this study, based on NUTS I

The Iberian energy system transition

Final energy demand

- Final energy demand decreases as the population is stable, the standard of living is high, and the system efficiency improves
- Massive shift towards electricity for final energy;
 - Reduction in heat sector demand due to use of direct electric heating and HPs
 - Significant reduction in transport sector demand mainly due to the electrification of road transport
 - Increase in industrial sector demand due to the sector's growth

Primary energy demand and fuels/chemicals supply

- Primary energy demand remains stable
- Oil dominance transitions to renewable electricity dominance
- Fuels use can be halved by using direct electrification whenever possible
- Remaining dominant fuels/chemicals are bio-based fuels, direct use of e-hydrogen, and e-methanol, and to a lesser extent, e-FTL (e-kerosene, e-diesel, e-naphtha) and e-ammonia for use in marine and aviation transport and industry

*Detailed assumptions and results can be found in the full paper

Figure 5. Final energy demand by source (top left) and sector (bottom left), primary energy demand by source (top right), and supply of fuels and chemicals (bottom right).

Electricity generation

Electricity capacities and generation

- Overall, solar PV dominates installed electricity capacities and generation
- Bifacial PV replaces most of the monofacial capacity in case of single-axis tracking systems as well as 11% of the wind power capacity
- Bifacial scenario:
 - PV capacity of 546 GW in 2040, of which: 48 GW prosumers, 17 GW monofacial and 0.3 GW bifacial fixed-tilted, 21 GW monofacial and 452 GW bifacial single-axis tracking, 8 GW vertical bifacial, and 0 GW offshore floating (mainland only)
 - Electricity generation increases from 289 TWh (2020) to 1318 TWh (2040)
 - Phasing out fossils and phasing in PV (87%), wind power (8%), and hydropower (5%) of electricity generation

Figure 6. Installed electricity capacity (left) and electricity generation (right) for the base scenario (top) and the bifacial scenario (bottom).

Regional electricity generation & trade

Figure 7. Regional electricity generation for the Bifacial scenario in 2040.

- Most of the electricity is generated in the southern regions of Spain and Portugal due to the better solar resources available there
 - Wind power is concentrated in the northern regions of Spain due to the better wind resources available there
- >> i.e., the South relies mostly on solar PV and the North also on wind power, and the North relies on the South and Central regions via electricity trade

Figure 8. Regional electricity trade for the Bifacial scenario in 2040.

- Noroeste (ES1): Net exporter
- Noreste (ES2): Net importer
- Madrid (ES3): Importer
- Centro (ES4): Exporter
- Este (ES5): Importer
- Sur (ES6): Net exporter
- Continente (PT1): Equal parts imports & exports

- The biggest exporting region is Central Spain at 46 TWh of electricity, followed by Southern Spain at 7 TWh
- The biggest importing region is Eastern Spain at 29 TWh, followed by Madrid at 12 TWh
- Portugal exports 2 TWh of electricity to Northwestern Spain and imports another 2 TWh from Central and Southern Spain
- Given the high electricity generation the system is almost balanced

Operational dynamics

Figure 9. Hourly state-of-charge for utility-scale battery (top left), operation of electrolyzers (top right), state-of-charge for hydrogen buffer storage (bottom right), and curtailment (bottom left) for the Bifacial scenario in 2040.

Dynamics of key energy system components

- Energy systems with very high shares of **variable renewables** (PV, wind) require **flexibility**: supply complementarity, demand response, sector coupling, grids, and storage
- Battery storage:**
 - Charging during the daytime and discharging in the afternoon/night
 - Slight seasonal variation
- Electrolyzers:**
 - Operation in hours of electricity availability, largely during the sunshine hours, and in the summer months with high solar energy yield
- Hydrogen storage:**
 - Operation mainly as a weekly buffer, but also with diurnal elements for optimal supply of baseload H₂-to-X synthesis
- Curtailment:**
 - Well balanced system with 8.4% electricity curtailment during peak solar production months as least cost solution

Costs and CO₂ emissions

Figure 10. LCOE (left) for the base (top) and bifacial (bottom) scenarios, LCO energy (top right) and sectoral CO₂ emissions (bottom right) for the Bifacial scenario.

Cost development

- Current (2020) LCOE stands at around 68 €/MWh, and is decreased by almost 60% by 2040 as the system transitions towards RE
- Deploying bifacial PV instead of its monofacial counterpart achieves LCOE savings of 1-3% on average during the transition period and increasing towards mid century
- High cost and inefficient non-renewable electricity is substituted largely by low-cost solar PV and battery balancing, among others
- Current (2020) LCO energy stands at around 50 €/MWh, and decreases by 17% by 2040 for the Bifacial scenario

CO₂ emissions development

- The power sector reaches zero CO₂ emissions by 2040
- The remaining CO₂ emissions are substantially lower (-90%) compared to the 240 MtCO₂ in 2020
- The remaining CO₂ emissions come from the relatively harder to defossilise sectors, such as heat, marine and aviation transport, and industry

Further benefits

- Improved trade balance & more jobs created
- Air pollution reduces with positive health impact

Energy flows in a Power-to-X Economy

Iberia v7 - 2040

Solar PV fixed tilted: 29,4
 Solar PV single-axis: 43,4
 Solar PV single-axis bifacial: 980,2
 Solar PV prosumers: 73,7
 Wind Onshore: 106,1
 Wind Offshore: 0,1
 Hydro RoR: 11,0
 Hydro Dam: 51,9

- Primary energy is dominated by **electricity**, complemented by some **solar thermal** and **bioenergy**
- The energy flow is described best as **Power-to-X Economy**, i.e.,
 - primary energy dominated by electricity,
 - direct electricity use as much as possible (e.g., electric vehicles, heat pumps),
 - strong sector coupling, and
 - indirect electrification by e-hydrogen-to-X (e-fuels, e-chemicals, e-steel) use if direct electricity is not possible
- High PV share** of 87% indicates rather a **Solar-to-X Economy**

Further reading on Power-to-X Economy:

- [Power-to-X economy: Breyer, Bogdanov, Ram, Khalili, Lopez, et al., 2022. Progress in Photovoltaics](#)
- [Breyer et al., 2023. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy](#)

Summary

➤ Iberia is very rich in renewable resources

- Electricity generation cost can be substantially reduced
- Overall energy system cost can be reduced
- More jobs can be created, trade balance improved, air pollution reduced and thus health improved
- Solar PV contributes the dominant share of energy supply complemented by some wind power and hydropower
- Electricity will emerge as the low-cost basis for a sustainable energy-industry system aiming for high efficiency standards
- Southern and central regions will emerge as electricity exporters owing to the higher solar energy yield in these regions, while the overall electricity exchange among regions is rather low at about 6% of generation

➤ Bifacial PV further improves the system performance

- Bifacial PV displaces most of the single-axis tracking monofacial PV capacity and some of the fixed-tilted monofacial PV and wind power capacities (-11%)
- Bifacial PV deployment leads to a higher curtailment (+0.1-0.7%abs), and more battery (+4%) and less hydrogen (-2%) storage
- This results in a 2% lower LCOE on average owing to the technology's higher yield and comparable cost

Thank you for your attention and to the team!

all publications at: www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=39761029000
new publications also announced via Twitter: [@ChristianOnRE](https://twitter.com/ChristianOnRE)

Солнечная экономика
Economía Solar
சூரிய அலைக்கதிர்வியல்
ಸೂರ್ಯ ಶಕ್ತಿ ಸಂವಹನ.
Күн экономика
SOLAR Economy
சூரிய ஆற்றல் சார்ந்த அமைப்புகள்
Solarökonomie
سولار ايكونومي
Árvinköztalans
Aje oorun
سولار ايكونومي
சூரிய ஆற்றல்
சூரிய ஆற்றல்